

Original Article

Effect of Current Density on Properties of Electrodeposited Nickel-Phosphorus Alloy Thin Films

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ABSTRACT

Electrode position in different current density was used to prepare nanostructure thin films of NiP. Films deposited with NiP have a texture that shows FCC structure. The structural properties of thin films observed experimentally for different current density were compared. The addition of phosphorus (Co) to nickel thin films will improve their structural and mechanical properties. Electrodeposited NiP films were prepared at various current density of 2,3,4 and 5 mA/cm². Morphological, structural, and mechanical characterization were performed on them. At 5 mA/cm², the nickel concentration reached its peak of 79.16wt%. As the current density was raised, the nickel content rose. NiP films were bright and evenly coated. NiP film deposits were also nano scale, with an average crystalline size of about 54 nm.

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INTRODUCTION

Electrode position is a simple and flexible approach for precisely controlling the nucleation and growth process in order to obtain catalysts of various purity, form, and morphology. Furthermore, electrode position is a scalable device that is used in a variety of manufacturing areas, making it ideal for large-scale applications [1-4]. Electrode position is a process of altering the surface structure of a substance using an electrochemical system [4-6]. The Ni-P alloy is one of the most researched materials because of its unique properties. I-P films as AMR sensors are widely used to detect weak magnetic fields in recording heads of magnetic data storage devices such as hard disks because of these properties [7-11]. The properties of iron-group metals such as iron and electro-deposited binary alloys have been improved by changing the deposition conditions [12-15]. The electrode position-based synthesis of nano crystalline nickel has gained a lot of attention [16-17]. The nature of crystallites and grain size of films are related to their soft magnetic nature. To boost traditional diamond tools, the grain size, hardness, and tensile strength of pulse electroformed nano crystalline NiP are used [17-19]. The

electrodeposition method is widely used in the MEMS, NEMS, communication, optical, and sensor industries. NiP, NiPW, and NiW are the most commonly found magnetic thin film compounds in MEMS and NEMS. NiP thin film electroplating is used to achieve improved structural and mechanical properties, unique optical properties, and increased corrosion resistance [20-23].

METHODS

Current density of 2,3,4 and 5 mA/cm² were used to prepare electroplated NiP alloy films. The deposition process took 15 minutes to complete. Copper and stainless steel substrates with dimensions of 1.5 cm x 7.5 cm were used as cathode and anode in this study [21-23]. Phosphorus acid (15 g/l), Nickel sulphate (30 g/l), Ammonium sulphate (40 g/l), Boric acid (10 g/l), and Saccharin (10 g/l) were used to make NiP thin films [23-25]. By adding ammonia solution, the pH of the electrolytic solution was set to 6.0, and the electroplating procedure was carried out with a temperature of 30 °C. After 15 minutes, the copper or cathode was gently removed from the bath and dried for a few minutes [24-25].

Scanning Electron Microscope was used to describe the surface nature of NiP films. Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy was used to look at the atomic composition of film deposits, and X-ray diffraction was used to look at the crystal structure of the deposits. Vickers Hardness Test was used to determine the micro hardness of the films.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Composition of Nip Films

The elemental composition of deposits is determined using an energy-dispersive X-ray analyzer (EDAX). EDAX study reveals the weight percentage of P and Ni at various current density in Table 1. According to the findings, films prepared at high current density have a high nickel content. At a current density of 2mA/cm², the maximum phosphorus content of 42.73wt% was found. The content of phosphorus decreases as the current density rises.

Table 1: EDAX analysis of thin films

S. No	Current density (mA/cm ²)	Ni Wt%	P Wt%
1.	2	57.37	42.63
2	3	66.04	33.96
3	4	73.74	26.26
4	5	79.16	20.84

Figure 1. Variation of weight percentage with different current density

Morphological Study of NiP Films

Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) images of the surface structure of NiP thin films at current density of 2,3,4 and 5 mA/cm² were analyzed, and the results are shown in Fig 2. On the result, the thin films are bright and uniformly coated. They appear to be crack-free.

Figure 2. NiP films –SEM images at (a) 2 (b) 3 (c) 4 (d) 5 mA/cm²

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF NiP FILMS

Powder X-ray diffraction was used to examine the crystal structure of NiP alloy films (XRD). Diffraction patterns of NiP films prepared at various current density are shown in Fig 2. The presence of sharp peaks in the X-ray diffraction pattern indicates that the deposits are crystalline. The XRD patterns of all samples deposited at current density of 2,3,4 and 5 mA/cm² shows (111), (200), and (220) peaks. In addition, the XRD results show the presence of an FCC form crystal. NiP deposits have particle sizes of 68.43 nm, 56.21 nm, 50.93 nm and 38.67 nm for current density of 2,3,4 and 5 mA/cm² respectively. As a result, increasing the current density reduces the crystal size of thin film deposits. Also deposits of thin films reveals nano scale and average crystalline size is around 54 nm.

Figure 3. NiP films-XRD patterns at (a) 2 (b) 3 (c) 4 (d) 5 mA/cm²

Table 2 shows the crystal dimension of NiP alloy films. If the bath temperature rises, the crystalline size of the deposits reduces owing to the start of crystal orientation. Figure 4 illustrates how crystal size decreases as bath temperature rises.

Table.2: Structural characteristics of NiPalloy thin films

S.No	Current density (mA/cm ²)	2θ (deg)	d (Å ⁰)	Particle Size(D) (nm)
1	2	45.88	1.5243	68.43
2	3	46.05	1.7452	56.21
3	4	44.63	1.6354	50.93
4	5	47.01	1.7104	38.67

Figure 4. Variation of crystal size with different current density

Mechanical Properties of Nip Films

Vickers hardness tester was used to measure the micro hardness of the deposits. Thin films prepared at current density of 2, 3, 4, and 5mA/cm² have hardness values of 93, 112, 143 and 175 VHN, respectively. As a result of the lower tension associated with thin films, the micro hardness increases. As the current density rises, micro hardness increases. Figure 5 illustrates how hardness changes as current density rises.

Figure 5. Variation of micro hardness with different current density

CONCLUSION

The NiP alloy thin films were prepared by electrodeposition at varying current density while maintaining a temperature of 30 ° C and a pH of 6.0 in the solutions. On the result, the thin films are bright and uniformly coated. The XRD results show that an FCC form crystal exists. If the current density rises, the crystalline size of the deposits decreases due to online crystal orientation. Due to the lower stress associated with thin films, the hardness increases as the current density rises. The particle size decreases from 68.43 nm to 38.67 nm as current density rises from 2 to 5mA/cm². This is due to the deposits of nano crystalline composition. As nickel is electroplated with phosphorus (P), the mechanical and structural properties improve, and the alloy films can be used in NEMS, MEMS, and memory units.

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REFERENCES

1. Nosang V, Park DY, Yoob BY, Paulo, TA. Development of electroplated magnetic materials for MEMS, Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials, 2003;265:189-198.
2. Meyers MA, Chawla KK. Mechanical Behavior of Materials, Prentice Hall, New Jersey, US, 1999, pp. 275.
3. Thompson CV. Structure evolution during processing of polycrystalline films, Annu. Rev. Mater. Sci. 2000; 30:159.
4. Chih-Huang L, Matsuyama H, White RL, Anthony TC, Anisotropic exchange for NiFe films grown on epitaxial NiO, IEEE Transactions on Magnetics 1995;31(6):2609-2611.
5. Emerson RN, Kennady CJ, Ganesan S. Effect of Organic additives on the Magnetic properties of Electrodeposition of CoNiP Hard Magnetic Films, Thin solid films. 2007; 515:3391-3396.
6. Iwasaki S, Nakamura Y. An analysis for the magnetization mode for high density magnetic recording, Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials. 1977; 200:634-648.
7. Ghorbani M, Dolati A, Afshar A. Electrodeposition of Ni-Fe Alloys in the Presence of Complexing Agents, Russ. J. Electrochem. 2002; 38:1173-1177.
8. Meyers MA, Chawla KK. Mechanical Behavior of Materials, Prentice Hall, New Jersey, US, 1999, pp. 275.
9. Bedir M, Bakkaloglu OF, Karahan IH, Oztas M. A study on electrodeposited Ni_xFe_{1-x} alloy films, Pramana. 2006;66(6):1093-1104.
10. Myung N. A Study on the Electrodeposition of NiFe Alloy Thin Films Using Chronocoulometry and Electrochemical Quartz Crystal Microgravimetry, Bull. Korean Chem. Soc. 2001; 22:994-998.
11. Esmaili S, Bahrololoom ME, Zamani C. Electrodeposition of NiFe/Cu multilayers from a single bath, Electron. Process. Mater. 2011;47(2):10-15.
12. Kannan R, Ganesan S, Selvakumari TM. Synthesis and characterization of nano crystalline NiFeWS thin films in diammonium citrate bath, Digest journal of nanomaterials and biostructures. 2012; 7:1039-1050.
13. Dixit G, Singh JP, Srivastava RC, Agrawal HM, Choudhary RJ, Ajay G. Structural and magnetic behavior of NiFe₂O₄ thin film grown by pulsed laser deposition, Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys. 2010;48:287-291.
14. Gupta N, Verma A, Kashyap SC. Dielectric behavior of spin-deposited nanocrystalline nickel-zinc ferrite thin films processed by citrate-route, Solid State Commun. 2005; 10:689-694.
15. Singh J, Gupta S, Singh A, Kothari P, Kotnala P, Akhtar J. Investigation of structural and magnetic properties of Ni, NiFe and NiFe₂O₄ thin films, Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials. 2012; 324:999-1005.
16. Esther P, Kennady C. Effect of sodium tungstate on the properties of Electrodeposited nanocrystalline NiP films, Journal of Non-Oxide Glasses. 2010; 1:35-44.
17. Hamid Z. Electrodeposition of Cobalt- Tungsten Alloys from Acidic Bath Containing Cationic Surfactants, Materials Letters. 2003; 57:2558.
18. Giouroudi I, Ktena A, Hristoforou E. Microstructural characterization of cylindrical Fe_{1-x}Ni_x thin films. J. Optoelectron. Adv. M. 2004; 6:661-666.
19. Motomura Y, Tatsumi T, Urai H, Aoyama M. Soft magnetic properties and heat stability for Fe/NiFe superlattices, IEEE Transactions on Magnetics 1990;26:2327-2331.

21. Kannan R, Ganesan S, Selvakumari TM. Structural and Magnetic properties of electrodeposited NiPS thin films, *Optoelectronics and advanced materials-Rapid Communication*. 2012;3(4):383-388.
22. Meng XF, Li DH, Shen XQ, Liu W. Preparation and magnetic properties of nano-Ni coated cenosphere Composites, *Applied Surface Science*. 2010; 256:3753–3756.
23. Sam S, Manavalan G, Guittoum A, Gabouze N, Djebbar S. Electrodeposition of NiFe films on Si(100) substrate, *Surf. Sci*. 2007; 601:4270–4273.
24. Celine R, Patrick F. Electrodeposition of thin films and nanowires Ni–Fe alloys, study of their magnetic susceptibility, *J, Mater Sci*. 2011;46:6046-6053.
25. Baonkeup K, Bongyoung Y. Electrodeposition of low-stress NiFe thin films from a highly acidic electrolyte, *Surf. Coat. Technol*. 2010; 205:740–744.
26. Tury B, Lakatos-Varsányi M, Roy S. Ni–Co alloys plated by pulse currents, *Surf. Coat. Technol*. 2006; 200:6713–6717.